

Known Probability Leading to Deterministic Average Behaviour?

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For a Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) gas probability is introduced through two body elastic scattering (particle-particle or particle-wall particle). One might argue that information is dropped in each microscopic two body interaction in the sense that a full set of information might exactly predict the collision. For example, in a collision of billiard balls one needs more information than the energy of each to fully analyse the collision. It is possible to drop information at microscopic single collision level, but then impose an average type of information i.e. argue that $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$ if $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4=E$. One might call this loss of information as stating that on average any $e_i+e_j=E$ has the same probability, but another way to consider this is that on average any $f(e_i)f(e_j)$ has the same probability if $e_i+e_j=E$. One may note that $f(e_i)f(e_j)$ are average quantities. For a given collision, however, an e_i, e_j may correspond to a full information set which may predict exactly the outcome.

We suggest that in an MB case, the collisions are the main driver of equilibrium and are related to impulse collisions linked to the momentum p . The collisions occur at x points and so p and x are connected in this way. This same argument holds in quantum mechanics so we suggest that phase space $x-p$ is used statistically because of its association with interactions rather than arguing that a Heisenberg uncertainty relation exists in quantum mechanics therefore x and p should be used to count states classically. The Heisenberg relation exists because p and x are already linked in $\exp(ipx)$ and this link, we argue, is due to impulses.

In the case of an MB gas with a potential, one may consider a tiny box of gas as having a constant density and balance pressure on each side with $-dV/dx$ density(x). This is a Newtonian “static” procedure applied to a system of probabilistic collisions. This approach leads to a density gradient. In the case of a flow problem it might suggest a sink or source, but this system is essentially governed by impulses and imposing an impulse balance in space may lead microscopically to a density gradient if a potential is present. Thus we argue that known probabilistic behaviour may give rise to static averages which are deterministic.

We also argue that a quantum free particle described by $\exp(ipx)$ follows this scenario, i.e. $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ are known probabilities distributions in x , but lead to the deterministic motion $x= p/m t$.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Gas Without a Potential

An MB gas in equilibrium in a container without a potential has a constant spatial density. An “information” argument is often given to account for this. In particular, it is stated that the region around each x point is the same, so if density differed, there would need to be “extra information” to account for this and such information does not seem to exist. Hence spatial density is constant.

Here we try to examine this situation in terms of the interactions which create the equilibrium. In an MB gas with a potential, one has Newtonian elastic scattering based on impulse hits (linked to p) which occur at x . There is probability because in terms of energy an i,j pair that satisfies:

$$e_i + e_j = E \quad ((1))$$

is considered to be as likely as another. Thus: $P(e_i + e_j) = P(e_i)P(e_j)$ ((2))
from which one may obtain the MB distribution.

For an equilibrium situation one expects a “static” average picture even though dynamics occurs for each single particle. How does this follow from a dynamic scattering scenario? Imagine that spatial density is lower in one box and higher in the adjacent. In such a case, particles from the high density box may flow (in a tiny time) with less scattering into the lower density box while a higher percentage of particles from the low density box will be reflected backwards when trying to enter the high density box. Thus the density of the high density box decreases and that of the low decreases. In fact, assuming the same energy distribution throughout the box, impulse collisions are still influenced by spatial density and one does not have equilibrium until the spatial density is constant. Thus, in addition to “information” arguments, one may argue for a constant spatial density by examining microscopic, stochastic collisions.

Already for the MB gas with no potential, one sees that equilibrium implies that many stochastic dynamic interactions may lead to a static constant density and this is due to a balance of impulses i.e. pressure as argued above. Thus one may apply Newton’s static force balance to a little box with many particles. In other words, a known probability distribution gives rise on average to a static picture which may be analysed in terms of deterministic mechanics. This approach becomes more useful when applied to an MB gas with a potential.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Gas with a Potential

Next we introduce a potential to the box. We wish again to describe this problem in terms of stochastic collisions because these are the microscopic basis of the gas. We shall do so in a qualitative manner. Consider three adjacent tiny boxes of gas (left to right) and take note of the density in the first and third. Imagine a potential which increases to the right.

Box 1 Some particles will move to the right towards box 3, but slow down in box 2. As a result, more of these particles will be reflected backwards (than if there were no $V(x)$) by particles in box 3. Thus a greater proportion than usual will be “sent” back to box 1. Furthermore box 3 will sense a weaker set of impulses on average.

Box 3 Some particles will move to the right and increase their speed and so arrive at box 1 with higher speeds. This leads to two effects. Fewer will be scattered backwards towards box 3 and stronger impulse hits will be felt. Thus a single particle with a higher p may impart the same impulse hit as two particles with lower p . One focuses on impulse hits and their balance and not on the number of particles.

Using the ideas related to box 1 and box 3, it seems box 1 should have a higher density than box 3. Box 1 sends extra particles to box 3, but they lose speed and a greater number than usual are reflected backwards. Furthermore the lower speeds give box 3 the sense of weaker

impulses which is consistent with fewer particles and regular impulses in box 3. In terms of box 1, particles from box 3 gain speed and so fewer reflect backwards. This may be partially compensated by the more than usual number of particles that move from box 1 to 3. They represent stronger impulses which match more particles with regular strength impulses in box 1.

As a result, one may use microscopic scattering arguments to suggest a lower density in box 3 than in box 1. To quantify this, one may move to the static deterministic picture of box 2 being in static Newtonian force balance with boxes 1 and 2. One needs a pressure expression for boxes 1 and 3 and this is given by the ideal gas law: $PV=nRT$ or Pressure = density RT .

Then:

$$-dV/dx \text{ density}(x) = RT \text{ d density}(x)/dx \quad ((3))$$

((3)) does appear to be related to dynamics, but pressure is given by a dynamical, statistical expression $P= \text{density} RT$ i.e. it is an entropic force/area. As a result, a stochastic system with microscopic dynamics may give rise in equilibrium to a static average picture which follows deterministic physics. In the MB gas, however, one may argue that deterministic physics exists all along as collisions, when fully analysed as in the case of billiard ball collisions, are deterministic. Dropping information to make the collisions probabilistic and then on average arguing that the dropped information is irrelevant (only in terms of averages) leads to a statistical picture which becomes deterministic in equilibrium.

Quantum Free Particle

In the above section, we argue that a seemingly deterministic system (albeit with a special entropic force/area = density(x) RT) has an underlying stochastic microscopic basis. This microscopic basis is linked to impulse hits based on single particle p momentum which take place at x points. Thus p and x are linked. In fact, one tries to create a “pressure” balance in x . If a potential is present (say increasing to the right), it shifts kinetic energies and momenta of particles moving to the right and left in a skewed way. Particles with higher momentum reaching a box on the left represent more impulse and so fewer are needed to create a balance. Fewer particles needed suggests fewer particles to begin with on the right. If there are more particles on the left, then more should move to the left (than for a particle balance), but they slow down due to the potential. This means more are reflected backwards and the rest represent weaker impulses. Even the “rest” still may represent a somewhat large number, but it compensates for the particles moving to the left which don’t reflect backwards due to their higher speed. Thus a balance of impulse is possible with a drop in density moving to the right. This leads to a static balance even though there is pressure within the system and microscopic probability.

A balance of force need not only lead to a static scenario, constant velocity also fits this picture. A quantum particle, such as an electron or photon, has constant speed and momentum. In Newtonian mechanics, it would be considered to move in the absence of forces, but we argue it might be possible to have microscopic “force” inherent in the quantum particle together with probabilities. $\exp(ipx)$, the free quantum wavefunction, suggests two probabilities distributions

$\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$, but these combine to yield an overall constant probability in x if one takes the modulus. Thus in quantum mechanics, one has the idea of p, x impulse as well as the notion of probabilistic internal force giving rise to a deterministic motion with forces balanced.

Role of the Translational Generator

It seems that to quantify the deterministic physics created from a stochastic one, one needs to consider the role of the translational generator. This generator is present in the analysis for both the MB and quantum free particle case. In the MB gas situation, the presence of d/dx implies there are changes in x , but a balance suggests they must combine to yield zero because there is no net momentum as a chunk of gas is not moving. Mathematically, this seems to be very similar to Fermat's least time scheme. In that scheme, one writes total time (say for reflection or refraction) in terms of x and takes d/dx so that $d/dx (t_1+t_2) = 0$. dt_1/dx and dt_2/dx turn out to momentum in the x direction and - momentum in the x direction and so one has a conservation of momentum in the x direction, which may be written in terms of a balance. For the MB gas, one has $d\text{Pressure}/dx$ balancing density $(-dV/dx)$. Thus there is a slight difference in that one has density $(-dV/dx)$ i.e. a function multiplied by a d/dx derivative, but the idea of creating a balance in x holds.

We argue that $\exp(ipx)$ for a quantum free particle also fits this scheme, because $-id/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$. Thus the d/dx generator shows that there is momentum in a certain direction. In the MB gas, $P=\text{density}(x)RT$ indicates impulse (related to momentum hits) in all directions at x , but if density changes with x , taking d/dx shows a net change in impulse (momentum hits) which balances with force from density $(x) (-dV/dx)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, systems in nature, such as an MB gas or a free quantum particle, may be viewed in terms of deterministic motion. For example, an MB gas with a potential may have its spatial density described by a Newtonian balance of forces (although an entropic force/are = density $(x)RT$ is needed). In this note, we try to examine how the balance is created through the microscopic stochastic collisions. We thus argue that a known probabilistic scenario may lead to average behaviour which is deterministic. We argue that this is also the case for a free quantum particle. We argue that to quantify these scenarios, use is made of the translational operator d/dx which is either linked with a balance (of force) (MB gas with potential) or a momentum flow i.e. Fermat's principle or a quantum free particle.